

Decoupling the One Dimensional Dirac Equations With a Scalar Potential

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In a previous note (1), it was noted one could write a solution of the bound state Schrodinger equation as $W(x)=W_0(x)D_n(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $W_0(x)$, the ground state wavefunction. Inserting into the Schrodinger equation one may obtain the Schrodinger equation for $W_0(x)$ and an equation coupling $W_0(x)$ and $D_n(x)$. In this note, we suggest such an approach may be applied to the one dimensional bound Dirac equations. This allows one to obtain decoupled equations for $u_1(x)$ and $v_1(x)$ where $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$ and $v(x)=v_1(x)v_0(x)$ are the full solutions. Thus, if one is able to obtain a solution for $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ by inspection, the decoupled equations allow one to find the general solution. We apply this approach to the case of a scalar potential $g|x|$. The Dirac problem for this potential has been solved in the literature (2) with decoupling occurring through the taking of spatial derivatives. Here we wish to suggest a general method.

Product Wavefunctions for the Dirac Bound Problem

Following (2), we write the coupled one dimensional bound Dirac equations as:

$$- \frac{d}{dx} v(x) = (E - m_0 - V(x)) u(x) \quad ((1))$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(x) = (E + m_0 + V(x)) v(x)$$

Next, we assume we have a simple solution to these equations (if possible). In the case of the $g|x|$ potential one may find these by inspection. We call these solutions $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ and their energy E_0 . These solutions need not be the ground state solution. Inserting into ((1)) and using the relationships:

$$u_1(x) \frac{d}{dx} u_0(x) - (m_0 + V(x)) u_1(x) u_0(x) = E_0 u_1(x) v_0(x) \quad \text{and}$$

$$-v_1(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_0(x) + (m_0 + V(x)) v_1(x) v_0(x) = E_0 v_1(x) u_0(x) \quad ((2))$$

One obtains:

$$u_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} u_1(x) = -E_0 u_1(x) v_0(x) + E v_1(x) v_0(x) \quad \text{and}$$

$$-v_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) = E u_0(x) u_1(x) - E_0 v_1(x) u_0(x) \quad ((3))$$

Decoupling Equations ((3))

The equations in ((3)) may now be decoupled for $v_1(x)$ and $u_1(x)$. One assumes, however, that one may obtain $v_0(x)$, $u_0(x)$ and E_0 in order for these equations to be useful. For example, one may write:

$$u_1(x) = [-v_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) + E_0 v_1(x) u_0(x)] / [E u_0(x)] \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u_1(x) = [-1/E^*E u_0^*u_0] [E (\frac{d}{dx} u_0(x)) [-v_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) + E_0 v_1(x) v_0(x)] + [1/E u_0(x)] [-v_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) - \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_0(x) + E_0 u_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x) + E_0 v_1(x) \frac{d}{dx} u_0(x)]$$

((4))

Then, one may insert these into:

$$u_0(x) \frac{d}{dx} u_1(x) + E_0 u_1(x) v_0(x) = E v_1(x) v_0(x) \quad ((5))$$

This yields a second order differential equation for $v_1(x)$ which is decoupled. A similar procedure may be used for $u_1(x)$.

The Dirac Bound Problem with $V(x) = g|x|$

The one dimensional problem with $V(x) = g|x|$ has been solved in (2) and the full details are not given here. We wish, however, to show one may use ((5)) to also solve the problem. ((5)) is a decoupled equation for $v_1(x)$ which makes no direct use of the potential. (A similar equation holds for $u_1(x)$). For example, we do not use of the idea of differentiating the Dirac equations because $g|x|$ is linear. The approach presented here should work for all potentials. The "catch" is one must be able to find a simple solution for $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$. Here we use inspection:

If one uses: $u_0 = y \exp(-y^2/2)$ and $v_0 = 1/E_0 \exp(-y^2/2)$ in the original Dirac equation ((1)) with $V(x) = gx$ for $x > 0$ then one may find that this is a solution by inspection for $y = dx + c$ where d and c are constants given in terms of m and g . Thus, a simple solution may be obtained and one may try to use ((5)) to find the full solution. Here we consider only $x > 0$ and $v_1(x)$ as an example.

We write $u_0 = C_1 y \exp(-y^2/2)$ and $v_0 = C_2 \exp(-y^2/2)$ but keep in mind that

$$C_2 E_0 = C_1. \quad ((6))$$

We also note that d/dy is the same as d/dx where $y = dx + c$.

We may insert ((4)) into ((5)) and consider coefficients of $d/dx \frac{d}{dx} v_1(x)$, $d/dx v_1(x)$ and $v_1(x)$. There is no constant term.

Coefficient of $d/dx d/dx v_1(x)$

$$u_0(x) E u_0(x) (-v_0(x)) = -y^*y C_1^*C_1^*C_2 E$$

Coefficient of $d/dx v_1(x)$

$$E_0 v_0(x) (-v_0(x) E u_0(x) + E u_0(x) (v_0(x) d/dx u_0(x)) + u_0(x) E u_0(x) [- d/dx v_0(x) + E_0 u_0(x)]) + E E_0 u_0 u_0 d/dx u_0$$

$$E_0 E (-1) y C_2^*C_2^*C + E C_1^*C_1^*C_2 y [1-y^*y] + E C_1 C_1 y^*y [C_2 y + E_0 C_2 y] + E E_0 C_1 C_1 C_1 y^*y [1 - y]$$

= Order(y^*y^*y) if one uses $C_2 E_0 = C_1$

$$-y^*y^*y E E_0 C_1 C_1 C_1 \quad (\text{Note: this factor divided by that of } d/dx d/dx v_1(x) \text{ yields 2.})$$

Coefficient of $v_1(x)$

$$-E v_0(x) E^*E u_0(x) u_0(x) + E_0 v_0(x) E u_0(x) E_0 u_0(x) - E u_0 (d/dx u_0) E_0 u_0 - E u_0 (d/dx u_0) u_0$$

The last two terms cancel leaving $-E v_0(x) E^*E u_0(x) u_0(x) + E_0 v_0(x) E u_0(x) E_0 u_0(x)$

$$= -E^*E^*E C_2 C_1 C_1 y^*y + E_0^*E_0^*E_1 C_2 C_1 C_1 y^*y$$

This expression is quadratic in y .

Thus, one finally obtains an equation for $v_1(x)$ of the form:

$$d/dy d/dy v_1(y) + 2 y d/dy v_1(y) + \text{constant } 3 v_1(y) = 0$$

Thus, one has the Hermite differential equation which yields Hermite polynomial solutions.

The general solution for $v(x)$ is $1/E_0 \exp(-y^*y/2) H_v(y)$ where $H_v(y)$ is a Hermite polynomial. The author of (2) shows v need not be an integer and also provides the solution for $u(x)$ for both $x > 0$

and $x < 0$. Here we simply present the above as a demonstration of a decoupling method for the one dimensional Dirac equations if one is able to find a simple solution $u_0(x)$, $v_0(x)$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we present a method for decoupling the one dimensional Dirac equation based on the idea that $u(x) = u_0(x)u_1(x)$ and $v(x) = v_0(x)v_1(x)$ where $u_0(x)$ and $v_0(x)$ are simple solutions that one may find easily, say by inspection. If one is able to obtain these, one may write two equations which have the scalar potential removed. The next step is to decouple which may be done easily as shown in ((4)) and ((5)). One may finally solve decoupled second order differential equations for $v_1(x)$ and $u_1(x)$. In this note, we have applied the approach to the Dirac problem for a potential of $g|x|$, finding the general solution for $x > 0$ for $v(x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Excited States (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Hiller, John Solution of the one dimensional Dirac equation with a linear scalar potential (2001) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/quant-ph/0111011.pdf>